
THE GEORGE
WASHINGTON
UNIVERSITY

WASHINGTON, DC

Black Friday

DATS 6103 - Individual project 3 - Tejaswini Vuppu

The dataset contains following list of variables.

- User_ID
- Product_ID
- Gender
- Age
- Occupation
- City_Category
- Stay_In_Current_City_Years
- Marital_Status
- Product_Category_1
- Product_Category_2
- Product_Category_3
- Purchase

Goals

- Visualizations
- Highest products have been purchased by people on black friday?
- Highest product category sold on that particular day?
- Among both genders male and female who pays the most?
- Among both the status single or married who buys the major?
- Regarding black Friday sales, what age group people are mostly curious?
- EDA
- To find the relation between Age vs Gender vs Marital Status

Source of Data

Black Friday data is taken from [kaggle.com](https://www.kaggle.com) (Links are provided in jupyter notebook) .This dataset contains study of sales through the consumer behaviours.

Gender, Purchase and Count

```
fig,ax = plt.subplots(nrows=1,figsize=(22,6),ncols=2)
sns.barplot(ax=ax[0],estimator=np.mean,x="Gender",data=dfRaw,y="Purchase").set_title('Gender Vs Purchase view')
sns.countplot(data=dfRaw,x="Gender",ax=ax[1]).set_title('Gender Vs Count')
```

```
Text(0.5, 1.0, 'Gender Vs Count')
```


Stay in City, Purchase and Count

```
fig,ax = plt.subplots(nrows=1,figsize=(22,6),ncols=2)
sns.barplot(x="Stay_In_Current_City_Years",y="Purchase",hue="City_Category",order=["0","1","2","3","4+"],estimator=np.mean)
sns.countplot(data=dfRaw,x="Stay_In_Current_City_Years",ax=ax[1],hue="City_Category",order=["0","1","2","3","4+"])
```

<matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot at 0x1a1bd88320>

City Category, Occupation and Purchase

```
fig,ax = plt.subplots(nrows=1,figsize=(22,6),ncols=2)
sns.violinplot(data=dfRaw,y="Occupation",ax=ax[0],x="City_Category")
sns.lineplot(data=dfRaw,y="Purchase",ax=ax[1],x="Occupation")
```

<matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot at 0x1a1f53ffd0>

Age, Occupation and Purchase

```
fig,ax = plt.subplots(nrows=1,figsize=(18,6),ncols=2)
sns.violinplot(data=dfRaw,y="Purchase",ax=ax[0],x="Age",order=["0-17","18-25","26-35","36-45","46-50","51-55","55+"])
sns.violinplot(data=dfRaw,y="Occupation",ax=ax[1],x="Age",order=["0-17","18-25","26-35","36-45","46-50","51-55","55+"])
```

<matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot at 0x1a232265f8>

Purchase

```
sns.boxplot(data=dfRaw, y="Purchase")
```

```
<matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot at 0x1a1ebdd2e8>
```


Highest products have been purchased by people on black friday?

- P00110742 is product_id which gives highest number of products with count of 159.
- Using this syntax, we get the answer for the question.
`dfRaw["Product_ID"].value_counts(sort=True)[:15]`
- By taking the count of people that have purchased the products, based on product_id and maximum number bought it.

Top 15 products based on Product_id and Count

P00110742	1591
P00025442	1586
P00112142	1539
P00057642	1430
P00184942	1424
P00046742	1417
P00059442	1384
P00145042	1384
P00237542	1374
P00010742	1331
P00110842	1260
P00102642	1228
P00242742	1194
P00034742	1188
P00080342	1186

Name: Product_ID, dtype: int64

Barplot of Top 15 Products

- More than 1100 in quantity are sold by the first 15 products.
- We can look at the data and say which products people are fascinated about obtaining.

Highest product category sold on that particular day?

Using this syntax, we get the answer for the question

```
#plotting the product category  
simple_bar_plot(dfRaw["Product_Category_1"].value_counts(sort=True)[:15],  
               title = "Top 15 Product Category of people interested")
```

Barplot to get top 15 product category people interested

When we see the data 1,2 and 5 have a range above 150K. And the products 10,11 and 13 have range up to 10K. There is tremendous change between first and last products of 15 items. Description of them is mentioned in the dataset, if we have a description we can check the data and get to know how many people are interested.

Among both genders male and female who pays the most?

Among both genders male and female who pays the most?(Continuation)

- Most of them are spend by females. When I look at the graph, it shows males.
- This is because female doesn't have enough money and the rest of the bills are paid by their spouses, who are males.
- This is the reason why the graph shows more data for males when compared with females. Now, let's see the marital status of buyers.

Among both the status single or married who buys the major?

```
#Let see  
count_plot(dfRaw, "Marital_Status", "Marital Status of Buyers")
```


Among both the status single or married who buys the major?(Continuation)

- When we look at the graph, there is plotting with value 0 & 1, which doesn't give much information about it.
- Now, let's again plot it with a proper legend.

Regarding black Friday sales, what age group people are mostly curious?

- Age group 26-35 are most curious with count of 65916.
- Using this syntax, we get the answer for the question.

```
dfRaw.Age.value_counts()
```

```
26-35      65916
36-45      32758
18-25      30889
46-50      13135
51-55      11018
55+         5773
0-17        4789
Name: Age, dtype: int64
```

Regarding black Friday sales, what age group people are mostly curious? (Continuation)

- Using this syntax, we get the answer for the question.

```
count_plot(dfRaw, "Age", "Age Group of  
Buyers")
```

Regarding black Friday sales, what age group people are mostly curious? (Continuation)

Among all age group people, most of them are from 26-35.

We can also find within age groups, which gender was the more by adding 'hue' parameter to the syntax.

When we look at it the majority is spent by males when compared with females.

EDA

- Let's see the Age group vs Marital status of the person based on Gender.
 - We need to group the persons buying in the age group and check the gender whether they are male or female.
 - We are also eager to know the marital status of them.
 - Using this syntax, we get the answer for the question.
- ```
count_plot(dfRaw,"Age","Age Group vs Marital Status", "Gender")
```

# EDA

- We have found a feature where we will connect the Gender & Marital Status.
- Then we will relate that with Age group



# To find the relation between Age vs Gender vs Marital Status

Using this syntax, we get the answer for the question.

```
dfRaw['combined_G_M'] = dfRaw.apply(lambda x: '%s_%s' % (x['Gender'], x['Marital_Status']), axis=1)
print(dfRaw['combined_G_M'].unique())
```

```
['F_0' 'M_1' 'M_0' 'F_1']
```

# To find the relation between Age vs Gender vs Marital Status(Continuation)

```
count_plot(dfRaw, "Age", "Age vs Gender vs Marital Status", "combined_G_M")
#dfRaw, "Age", "Age vs Gender vs Marital Status", "combined_G_M"
```



# Conclusion

According to barplot above, there are no bars in the range 0-17 for married (M\_1) and Female (F\_1) which gives us some information. When we see age groups from 46 and above, Females are doing less when compared with males. On the contrast, when we look at the married men investing more money on Black Friday sales associated with married women.

# Conclusion...2

We all knew that women do shopping a lot but their spouses i.e., husband sponsor money for them. So the data reflects as it is men's expense. If we know some more information like categorical data about products purchased by men, we might have gone some more detailed into it. Finally, I conclude saying that, we don't know until unless there is a category that belongs to feminine products/clothes in this dataset. We cannot effort much time examining this topic.

# References

- <https://www.kaggle.com/>
- <https://pandas.pydata.org/>
- <http://www.numpy.org/>
- <https://matplotlib.org/>